

Machine learning discoveries of PLK4-X synergy in ETC-1922159 treated colorectal cancer cells

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Abstract

Polo like kinase 4 (PLK4) is a serine/threonine-protein kinase that localizes to centrioles and regulates centriole duplication during the cell cycle. Overexpression of PLK4 causes centrosome amplification, and its knockdown leads to loss of centrosomes. In colorectal cancer (CRC) cells treated with ETC-1922159, PLK4 was found to be down regulated along with other genes. A recently developed search engine ranked combinations of PLK4-X (X, a particular gene/protein) at 2^{nd} order level after drug administration. Some of these combinations have been tested in wet lab, however many have been pointed out by the search engine that are yet to be explored/tested. These rankings reveal which PLK4-X combinations might be working synergistically in CRC. In this research work, I cover combinations of PLK4 with possible members of aurora kinase (AURK), centrosomal protein (CEP), ubiquitin specific peptidase (USP), E2F transcription factor (E2F), epithelial cell transforming 2 (ECT2), STIL centriolar assembly protein (STIL), cell division cycle (CDC), cell division cycle associated (CDCA), cyclin dependent kinase (CDK), forkhead box (FOX), kinesin family member (KIF) and small nucleolar RNA host gene (SNHG) family.

Keywords: PLK4, Porcupine inhibitor ETC-1922159, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning, Colorectal cancer.

1. Introduction

1.1. PLK4

PLK4 as a key regulator of centriole duplication (Habedanck et al. [1]). Centriole duplication is tightly controlled to prevent cells from developing multipolar spindles (which promotes chromosomal instability). To limit centriole duplication, PLK4 levels

^{*}ML discoveries of PLK4-X synergy in ETC-1922159 treated CRC cells

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are controlled through trans-autophosphorylation. Slevin et al. [2] studied its structure and find that it possesses a central region called the cryptic polo box, which reveals two homodimerized polo boxes, PB1-PB2. Thus, with its C-terminal polo box (PB3), PLK4 has a triple polo box architecture that promotes trans-autophosphorylation, limiting centriole duplication to once per cell cycle and facilitates oligomerization and targeting. High frequency of centrosome amplification has been reported in more aggressive tumors. Godinho et al. [3] show that centrosome amplification induced by PLK4 resulted in the formation of invasive protrusions that invade the surrounding matrix. Chan [4] provide a review of mechanisms of centrosome amplification in various cancers and also provide references that implicate the role of PLK4 in centrosome amplification. More recently, Liao et al. [5] show that overexpression of PLK4 promotes tumor progression and induces EMT by regulating the WNT/ β -catenin pathway in colorectal cancer. In colorectal cancer (CRC) cells treated with ETC-1922159, PLK4 was found to be down regulated along with other genes. Some combinations of PLK4 have been confirmed in wet lab, however, many of the combinations have not been explored/tested or are known. To reveal these combinations, I use a modification of a recently published machine learning based search engine, details of which are given in the next section.

1.2. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [6], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Readers are requested to go through the adaptation of the above mentioned work for gaining deeper insight into the working of the pipeline and its use of published data set generated after administration of ETC-1922159, Sinha [7]. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [8] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene combinations.

2. Results & Discussion

2.1. PLK4 related synergies

2.1.1. PLK4 - AURK

Luo et al. [9] observe that CEP192, PLK4 and AURKB/C associate with the WNT-PCP protein DVL2 and DVL2 recruits CEP192/PLK4/AURKB module to promote protrusive activity and cell motility by mediating a kinase-dependent switch of DAAM1 for DAAM2. Thus there is synergy between PLK4 and AURK family. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, AURK family members and PLK4, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of these AURK members along with PLK4.

Table 1 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 2 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1. The table 1 shows rankings of AURK members w.r.t PLK4. AURKB - PLK4 shows low ranking of 1339 (laplace), 1268 (linear) and 586 (rbf). These rankings point to the

synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, AURKA showed high ranking with PLK4, thus indicating that they might not be working synergistically with PLK4, before the drug treatment.

RANKING AURK FAMILY VS PLK4			
RANKING OF AURK FAMILY W.R.T PLK4			
	laplace	linear	rbf
AURKB - PLK4	1339	1268	586
AURKA - PLK4	2247	617	1930

Table 1: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between PLK4 VS AURK members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 graphically, with the following influences - • AURK members w.r.t PLK4 with PLK4 - > AURK-B.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
AURK members w.r.t PLK4	
AURK-B	PLK4

Table 2: 2^{nd} order combinatorial hypotheses between PLK4 and AURK members.

2.1.2. PLK4 - CEP

From the previous section, Luo et al. [9] also show that upon ACM (active-conditioned-medium) treatment, CEP192 isoform-1 specifically recruits active PLK4, while other CEP192 isoforms can recruit active AURKB. Further, Sullenberger et al. [10] dissected centrosomal localization of PLK4 in G1 and S phase and find that CEP57, CEP63, CEP44, and CEO192 localize in ninefold symmetry. During centriole maturation, they propose that CEP152 (a receptor of PLK4) molecular arrangement creates flexibility for PLK4 and procentriole placement during centriole initiation. Thus there is synergy between PLK4 and CEP family. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, CEP family members and PLK4, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of these CEP members along with PLK4.

Table 3 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 4 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 3. The table 3 shows rankings of CEP members w.r.t PLK4. CEP70 - PLK4 shows low ranking

of 42 (laplace) and 660 (rbf). CEP152 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 337 (laplace) and 1017 (rbf). CEP76 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 395 (laplace) and 272 (rbf). CEP68 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 458 (laplace), 1537 (linear) and 251 (rbf). CEP55 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 357 (laplace), 474 (linear) and 676 (rbf). CEP57 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 945 (laplace) and 673 (rbf). CEP250 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 1057 (laplace), 1134 (linear) and 642 (rbf). CEP192 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 1109 (laplace), 1146 (linear) and 742 (rbf). CEP44 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 1127 (laplace) and 1003 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment. Of importance is the fact that the engine pointed out correct/appropriate results for CEP192, CEP152, CEP57 and CEP44 combination with PLK4, as cited in literature above.

Further, CEP164P1, CEP128, CDP41 and CEP78 showed high ranking with PLK4, thus indicating that they might not be working synergistically with PLK4, before the drug treatment.

RANKING CEP FAMILY VS PLK4							
RANKING OF CEP FAMILY W.R.T PLK4							
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
CEP70 - PLK4	42	2078	660	CEP152 - PLK4	337	2095	1017
CEP76 - PLK4	395	2444	272	CEP68 - PLK4	458	1537	251
CEP55 - PLK4	357	474	676	CEP57 - PLK4	945	2286	673
CEP250 - PLK4	1057	1134	642	CEP192 - PLK4	1109	1146	742
CEP44 - PLK4	1127	1633	1003	CEP164P1 - PLK4	1951	2319	993
CEP128 - PLK4	2208	130	2502	CEP41 - PLK4	2525	552	2283
CEP78 - PLK4	2594	84	2477				

Table 3: 2nd order interaction ranking between PLK4 VS CEP members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 3 graphically, with the following influences - • CEP members w.r.t PLK4 with PLK4 – > CEP-70/152/76/68/55/57/250/192/44.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

CEP members w.r.t PLK4

CEP-70/152/76/68/55/57/250/192/44 PLK4

Table 4: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between PLK4 and CEP members.

2.1.3. PLK4 - USP

The role of centrosomal protein in centrosome replication is established and their overexpression can lead to centrosome duplicate abnormality, which is closely associated with tumorigenesis and development. Zhang et al. [11] have demonstrated that CEP120 promotes centrosome amplification and gastric cancer (GC) progression by

USP54-mediated deubiquitination of PLK4. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, USP family members and PLK4, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these USP members along with PLK4.

Table 5 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 6 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 5. The table 5 shows rankings of USP members w.r.t PLK4. USP39 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 14 (laplace) and 881 (rbf). USP10 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 325 (laplace) and 931 (rbf). USP1 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 592 (laplace), 1415 (linear) and 938 (rbf). USP28 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 645 (linear) and 1451 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, USP36 and USP13 showed high ranking with PLK4, thus indicating that they might not be working synergistically with PLK4, before the drug treatment.

RANKING USP FAMILY VS PLK4

RANKING OF USP FAMILY W.R.T PLK4			
	laplace	linear	rbf
USP39 - PLK4	14	2042	881
USP10 - PLK4	325	2285	931
USP1 - PLK4	592	1415	938
USP28 - PLK4	1725	645	1451
USP36 - PLK4	1813	2478	1202
USP13 - PLK4	2191	148	2630

Table 5: 2nd order interaction ranking between PLK4 VS USP members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 5 graphically, with the following influences - • USP members w.r.t PLK4 with PLK4 – > USP-39/10/1/28.

2.1.4. PLK4 - E2F

In breast cancer cells, Lee et al. [12] observed that overexpression of E2F1, E2F2, or E2F3 increased centrosome amplification and revealed that E2Fs affect the expression of PLK4. They also show that PLK4 is strongly correlated with E2F factors and is a direct transcriptional target of E2F activators. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, E2F family members and PLK4, were found to be down regulated and

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

USP members w.r.t PLK4

USP-39/10/1/28 **PLK4**

Table 6: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between PLK4 and USP members.

their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these E2F members along with PLK4.

Table 7 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 8 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 7. The table 7 shows rankings of E2F members w.r.t PLK4. E2F5 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 84 (laplace) and 898 (rbf). E2F7 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 269 (laplace) and 629 (linear). E2F8 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 973 (laplace), 606 (linear) and 747 (rbf). E2F1 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 1193 (laplace) and 304 (linear). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, E2F2 showed high ranking with PLK4, thus indicating that they might not be working synergistically with PLK4, before the drug treatment.

RANKING E2F FAMILY VS PLK4							
RANKING OF E2F FAMILY W.R.T PLK4							
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
E2F5 - PLK4	84	2574	898	E2F7 - PLK4	269	629	1720
E2F8 - PLK4	973	606	747	E2F1 - PLK4	1193	304	1765
E2F2 - PLK4	2152	499	2295				

Table 7: 2nd order interaction ranking between PLK4 VS E2F members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 7 graphically, with the following influences - • E2F members w.r.t PLK4 with PLK4 – > E2F-5/7/8/1.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

E2F members w.r.t PLK4

E2F-5/7/8/1 **PLK4**

Table 8: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between PLK4 and E2F members.

2.1.5. PLK4 - ECT2 / STIL

Rosario et al. [13] show that PLK4 normally localizes to the midbody and binds to and phosphorylates ECT2. Further, they show that loss of heterozygosity (LOH) occurs at the Plk4 locus in 50% of human hepatocellular carcinomas (HCC) and is associated with reduced PLK4 expression in HCC tumors, which causes failure to localize the ECT2 to the spindle midbody, as one of the phenotypes. Moyer et al. [14] have discovered a molecular basis for the timing of PLK4 activation through accumulation of STIL and show that direct binding of STIL activates PLK4 by promoting self-phosphorylation of the activation loop of the kinase. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these individual members and PLK4, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of these individual members along with PLK4.

Table 9 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 10 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 9. The table 9 shows rankings of INDIVIDUAL members w.r.t PLK4. ECT2 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 382 (laplace), 1493 (linear) and 582 (rbf). STIL - PLK4 shows low ranking of 132 (laplace) and 171 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment. It is important to note that in the light of the observations in the above literature about the established connection of a member (here ECT2/STIL), we find that the combination of the same with PLK4 gets appropriate ranking in colorectal cancer cells also, thus confirming the possible existence of synergy.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL FAMILY VS PLK4			
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL FAMILY W.R.T PLK4			
	laplace	linear	rbf
ECT2 - PLK4	382	1493	582
STIL - PLK4	132	2010	171

Table 9: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between PLK4 VS individual members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 9 graphically, with the following influences - • individual members w.r.t PLK4 with PLK4 – > ECT2/STIL.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
Individual members w.r.t PLK4	
ECT2/STIL	PLK4

Table 10: 2^{nd} order combinatorial hypotheses between PLK4 and individual members.

2.1.6. PLK4 - CDC

Bonni et al. [15] show that CDC25C is a substrate of PLK4 as both wild type and kinase active forms of the latter were able to phosphorylate CDC25C. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, CDC family members and PLK4, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. Additionally, I report the combinations of cell division cycle associated (CDCA) with PLK4 also. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these CDC/CDCA members along with PLK4.

Table 11 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 12 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 11. The table 11 shows rankings of CDC members w.r.t PLK4. CDC123 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 16 (laplace) and 735 (rbf). CDC25C - PLK4 shows low ranking of 321 (laplace), 424 (linear) and 648 (rbf). CDC23 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 322 (laplace), 1389 (linear) and 485 (rbf). CDC25A - PLK4 shows low ranking of 622 (laplace), 171 (linear) and 730 (rbf). CDC45 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 990 (laplace), 1469 (linear) and 1512 (rbf). CDC6 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 1548 (laplace) and 517 (linear) CDC20 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 701 (linear) and 1515 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment. Additionally, in line with the above literature reference, we find appropriate ranking of CDC25C with PLK4 in colorectal cancer case treated with ETC-1922159, thus pointing towards possible synergy in CRC.

Further, CDC7 showed high ranking with PLK4, thus indicating that they might not be working synergistically with PLK4, before the drug treatment.

The table 11 also shows rankings of CDCA members w.r.t PLK4. CDCA3 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 208 (laplace) and 149 (rbf) CDCA7 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 585 (laplace) and 186 (rbf) CDCA7L - PLK4 shows low ranking of 1165 (laplace), 626 (linear) and 1243 (rbf) CDCA5 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 1206 (laplace) and 615 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, CDCA8, CDCA2 and CDCA4 showed high ranking with PLK4, thus indicating that they might not be working synergistically with PLK4, before the drug treatment.

One can also interpret the results of the table 11 graphically, with the following influences - • CDC members w.r.t PLK4 with PLK4 – > CDC-123/25C/23/25A/45/6/20 and • CDCA members w.r.t PLK4 with PLK4 – > CDCA-3/7/7L/5.

2.1.7. PLK4 - CDK

Franck et al. [16] found that PLK4 and CEP192, showed reduced levels at centrosomes of mitotic CDK11-depleted cells. CDK11^{p58}, which accumulates only in the vicinity of mitotic centrosomes, directly interacts with the centriole-associated PLK4. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, CDK family members and PLK4, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these CDK members along with PLK4.

Table 13 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored

RANKING CDC FAMILY VS PLK4

RANKING OF CDC FAMILY W.R.T PLK4			
	laplace	linear	rbf
CDC123 - PLK4	16	2506	735
CDC25C - PLK4	321	424	648
CDC23 - PLK4	322	1389	485
CDC25A - PLK4	622	171	730
CDC45 - PLK4	990	1469	1512
CDC6 - PLK4	1548	517	2224
CDC20 - PLK4	1677	701	1515
CDC7 - PLK4	1834	2039	1913
RANKING CDCA FAMILY VS PLK4			
RANKING OF CDCA FAMILY W.R.T PLK4			
	laplace	linear	rbf
CDCA3 - PLK4	208	2363	149
CDCA7 - PLK4	585	2152	186
CDCA7L - PLK4	1165	626	1243
CDCA5 - PLK4	1206	1941	615
CDCA8 - PLK4	1557	2092	1041
CDCA2 - PLK4	2103	274	2233
CDCA4 - PLK4	2278	1298	1966

Table 11: 2nd order interaction ranking between PLK4 VS CDC members.

combinatorial hypotheses in table 14 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 13. The table 13 shows rankings of CDK members w.r.t PLK4. CDK5RAP2 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 156 (laplace) and 73 (rbf). CDK6 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 552 (laplace), 1329 (linear) and 322 (rbf). CDK20 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 797

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

CDC members w.r.t PLK4	
CDC-123/25C/23/25A/45/6/20	PLK4
CDCA members w.r.t PLK4	
CDCA-3/7/7L/5	PLK4

Table 12: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between PLK4 and CDC members.

(laplace) and 901 (linear). CDK1 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 1035 (laplace), 432 (linear) and 585 (rbf). CDK4 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 1045 (laplace) and 977 (rbf). CDK5RAP1 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 1501 (laplace), 688 (linear) and 821 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

RANKING CDK FAMILY VS PLK4

RANKING OF CDK FAMILY W.R.T PLK4			
	laplace	linear	rbf
CDK5RAP2 - PLK4	156	2724	73
CDK6 - PLK4	552	1329	322
CDK20 - PLK4	797	901	1845
CDK1 - PLK4	1035	432	585
CDK4 - PLK4	1045	2440	977
CDK5RAP1 - PLK4	1501	688	821

Table 13: 2nd order interaction ranking between PLK4 VS CDK members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 13 graphically, with the following influences - • CDK members w.r.t PLK4 with PLK4 – > CDK-5RAP2/6/20/1/4/5RAP1.

2.1.8. PLK4 - FOX

Penailillo et al. [17] shown that reduced FOXM1 expression limits trophoblast migration and angiogenesis in choriocarcinoma cell lines, and in a rat model, placental FOXM1 expression was upregulated in the early stages of pregnancy. Further, for the

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

CDK members w.r.t PLK4

CDK-5RAP2/6/20/1/4/5RAP1 PLK4

Table 14: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between PLK4 and CDK members.

first time, they demonstrate that FOXM1 is present in the trophectoderm of mice blastocysts and confirm that maternal-fetal communication is crucial for trophoblast invasion and that maternal stromal cells may induce trophoblast cells to express high levels of FOXM1, leading to transcriptional activation of downstream target gene PLK4. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, FOX family members and PLK4, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these FOX members along with PLK4.

Table 15 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 16 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 15. The table 15 shows rankings of FOX members w.r.t PLK4. FOXM1 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 1466 (laplace), 1312 (linear) and 750 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment. In line with the above evidence in literature, the engine assigns appropriate rankings for FOXM1-PLK4 combination, thus possibly confirming the existence of the synergy in colorectal cancer.

Further, FOXD2-AS1, FOXA2 and FOXJ1 showed high ranking with PLK4, thus indicating that they might not be working synergistically with PLK4, before the drug treatment.

RANKING FOX FAMILY VS PLK4			
RANKING OF FOX FAMILY W.R.T PLK4			
	laplace	linear	rbf
FOXD2-AS1 - PLK4	623	1829	1591
FOXA2 - PLK4	1320	1649	1684
FOXM1 - PLK4	1466	1312	750
FOXJ1 - PLK4	2224	49	2476

Table 15: 2nd order interaction ranking between PLK4 VS FOX members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 15 graphically, with the following influences - • FOX members w.r.t PLK4 with PLK4 – > FOX-M1.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

FOX members w.r.t PLK4

FOX-M1	PLK4
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Table 16: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between PLK4 and FOX members.

2.1.9. PLK4 - KIF

In endometrial cancer, Zhou et al. [18] demonstrated that KIFC1 inhibited E3 ubiquitin-protein ligase TRIM37 expression, which lead to reduction of ubiquitination degradation of PLK4 and maintained its stabilization, to promote centrosome amplification and progression. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, KIF family members and PLK4, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these KIF members along with PLK4.

Table 17 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 18 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 17. The table 17 shows rankings of KIF members w.r.t PLK4. KIF13A - PLK4 shows low ranking of 2 (laplace) and 944 (rbf). KIF11 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 18 (laplace), 1058 (linear) and 1082 (rbf). KIF20A - PLK4 shows low ranking of 477 (laplace), 1220 (linear) and 859 (rbf). KIF4A - PLK4 shows low ranking of 664 (laplace), 398 (linear) and 640 (rbf). KIF15 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 834 (laplace) and 622 (rbf). KIF2C - PLK4 shows low ranking of 927 (laplace), 1438 (linear) and 994 (rbf). KIF18B - PLK4 shows low ranking of 954 (laplace) and 1186 (rbf). KIF14 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 955 (laplace), 1036 (linear) and 916 (rbf). KIF27 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 993 (laplace), 1277 (linear) and 1187 (rbf). KIF18A - PLK4 shows low ranking of 1014 (laplace), 306 (linear) and 901 (rbf). KIF23 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 1242 (laplace), 1193 (linear) and 801 (rbf). KIF22 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 70 (linear) and 1401 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment. In line with the above evidence in literature, the engine assigns appropriate rankings for KIFM1-PLK4 combination, thus possibly confirming the existence of the synergy in colorectal cancer.

Further, KIF9, KIF20B, KIFC1 and KIF7 showed high ranking with PLK4, thus indicating that they might not be working synergistically with PLK4, before the drug treatment. Important to note is that, in line with the combination of KIFC1-PLK4, the engine did not rank it appropriately for colorectal cancer cells. The high rank assigned to the combination in the colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, indicate that it might NOT have been working synergistically in CRC before treatment.

One can also interpret the results of the table 17 graphically, with the following influences - • KIF members w.r.t PLK4 with PLK4 – > KIF-M1.

RANKING KIF FAMILY VS PLK4							
RANKING OF KIF FAMILY W.R.T PLK4							
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
KIF13A - PLK4	2	1741	944	KIF11 - PLK4	18	1058	1082
KIF20A - PLK4	477	1220	859	KIF4A - PLK4	664	398	640
KIF15 - PLK4	834	1691	622	KIF2C - PLK4	927	1438	994
KIF18B - PLK4	954	1851	1186	KIF14 - PLK4	955	1036	916
KIF27 - PLK4	993	1277	1187	KIF18A - PLK4	1014	306	901
KIF23 - PLK4	1242	1193	801	KIF22 - PLK4	1891	70	1401
KIF9 - PLK4	1933	1877	1960	KIF20B - PLK4	2462	405	2517
KIFC1 - PLK4	2562	880	1999	KIF7 - PLK4	2610	765	2440

Table 17: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between PLK4 VS KIF members.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
KIF members w.r.t PLK4	
KIF-13A/11/20A/4A/15/2C/18B/14/27/18A/23/22	PLK4

Table 18: 2^{nd} order combinatorial hypotheses between PLK4 and KIF members.

2.1.10. PLK4 - SNHG

In neuroblastoma cells, Xu et al. [19] showed by western blot analysis that miR-338-3p negatively regulated PLK4 expression, and miR-338-3p re-expression could reverse SNHG16 overexpression, which instigated an increase of PLK4 expression in SK-N-AS-R and SK-N-SH-R cells. These results suggested that SNHG16/miR-338-3p/PLK4 axis could regulate the activation of PI3K/AKT pathway in neuroblastoma cells. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, SNHG family members and PLK4, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of these SNHG members along with PLK4.

Table 19 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 20 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 19. The table 19 shows rankings of SNHG members w.r.t PLK4. SNHG18 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 238 (laplace), 1392 (linear) and 339 (rbf). SNHG15 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 928 (laplace), 1549 (linear) and 1288 (rbf). SNHG7 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 1022 (laplace) and 839 (rbf). SNHG17 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 1052 (laplace), 1159 (linear) and 925 (rbf). SNHG3 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 1115 (laplace) and 1005 (rbf). SNHG6 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 1260 (laplace) and 835 (rbf). SNHG8 - PLK4 shows low ranking of 1288 (laplace) and 582 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, SNHG1, SNHG16, SNHG5 and SNHG10 showed high ranking with PLK4, thus indicating that they might not be working synergistically with PLK4, before the

drug treatment. Important to note is that, in line with the combination of SNHG16-PLK4 which was found to be established in neuroblastoma (as mentioned in the above literature), the engine did not rank it appropriately for colorectal cancer cells. The high rank assigned to the combination in the colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, indicate that it might NOT have been working synergistically in CRC before treatment.

RANKING SNHG FAMILY VS PLK4

	laplace	linear	rbf
SNHG18 - PLK4	238	1392	339
SNHG15 - PLK4	928	1549	1288
SNHG7 - PLK4	1022	2033	839
SNHG17 - PLK4	1052	1159	925
SNHG3 - PLK4	1115	1659	1005
SNHG6 - PLK4	1260	1985	835
SNHG8 - PLK4	1288	2311	582
SNHG1 - PLK4	1802	2281	1115
SNHG16 - PLK4	2050	1321	2150
SNHG5 - PLK4	2098	1280	1815
SNHG10 - PLK4	2711	956	2658

Table 19: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between PLK4 VS SNHG members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 19 graphically, with the following influences - • SNHG members w.r.t PLK4 with PLK4 – > SNHG-18/15/7/17/3/6/8.

3. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic PLK4 2^{nd} order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of PLK4-X that might be prevalent in CRC cells after treatment with ETC-1922159 drug.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

SNHG members w.r.t PLK4

SNHG-18/15/7/17/3/6/8	PLK4
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Table 20: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between PLK4 and SNHG members.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

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Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Madan et al. [20].

4. References

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